

A review on thermo-acoustic investigations of food preservatives at multiple mixtures

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Abstract- The degree of ideal and non-ideal liquid combinations of food preservatives are needed to be researched as they find their wide applications in food industries. Through the use of several quantifiable qualities, various properties can be measured empirically. They can also be approximated using a variety of model equations. Density and sound speed are primary indicators of these liquid mixes and may be used in conjunction with thermodynamic principles to derive a wide range of volumetric and acoustic parameters. All thermodynamic and volumetric parameters are sensitive to changes in pressure and temperature. Additional features include thermal expansion coefficients, isothermal pressure coefficients, and thermal expansion coefficients with excess. The thermo-acoustic studies and research on food preservatives are summarized in the present review.

Keywords- Ideal and non-ideal liquid, thermal expansion coefficients, excess thermal expansion coefficients, isothermal coefficients of pressure, thermodynamic and volumetric properties

I. Introduction

A Greek philosopher 'Pythagoras' is considered to have invented the study of acoustics (6th century bc). The rules of thermodynamics provide a detailed analysis of all variations in a system's energy state and its capacity to improve its surroundings. For the prediction of intermolecular interactions in liquid mixtures, the ultrasonic method is effective. The distinct characteristic of sound wave property is that it provides clear, accurate information on the characteristics of the solution [1-6] Density, viscosity, ultrasonic velocity, acoustic, thermodynamic, excess thermodynamic, and their variations have all been the subject of numerous recent research, particularly in the context of binary and ternary systems. An ultrasonic velocity measurement is an essential tool for studying intra- and intermolecular interactions in liquids. Mixed solvents, as compared to pure liquids, are more commonly used in industrial and chemical processes. [7] Nowadays, the majority of food is packaged, making it quite safe for everyone to consume top-quality preserved food.

A Review on Thermo-acoustic Investigations of Food Preservatives at Multiple Mixtures

Acoustic and volumetric techniques are used to examine the intermolecular interactions between polyethylene glycol molecules in aqueous D-mannitol solutions. The density and sound speed of ternary mixtures using an Anton Paar DSA 5000 M. Because liquid mixtures have a wide range of desirable qualities, they frequently have more applications than pure liquids. For the purpose of analyzing and comprehending the physicochemical behavior of liquid mixes, volumetric and acoustical aspects are crucial. Understanding these characteristics is a crucial tool for determining how various chemical compounds interact when mixed together. According to research by H. Kaur et al. [1] sound speed improves as temperatures rise.

K. P. Patnaik et al. [2] report that this non-destructive method was an indispensable resource for understanding the molecular interactions occurring within the liquid system they studied. Due to the potent molecular interactions between the molecules of the two phases, it has been discovered that the adiabatic compressibility is inversely proportional to the concentration of either the solute or the solvent. The adiabatic compressibility diminishes when the free length shrinks and the molecules are packed closer together. When the concentration of a mixture is increased, the value of Vander Waal's Constant decreases, indicating that the molecules interact with one another less strongly.

At different times and temperatures, we used the Anton Paar DSA 5000M to determine the density and sound speed of ethylene, diethylene and triethylene glycols (EG, DEG, and TEG) in a D-mannitol aqueous solution. The intermolecular free length, acoustic impedance, adiabatic compression, Wada's constant, Rao's constant, and Vander Waal's factor are only some of the other theoretical parameters that can be determined from density and sound speed data. If you want to understand how polar and non-polar liquids interact with one another on a molecular level, you'll need to use an ultrasonic method. The structure and internal interactions of the system have a significant impact on the sound wave

speed. Understanding these characteristics is a crucial tool for determining how chemical substances interact when mixed has been studied by H. Kaur et al. [3]

We determine the acoustic pressure and volume of a liquid mixture The ultrasonic approach has been proven to be exceptionally precise and dependable for evaluating the acoustic and volumetric characteristics of diverse liquid mixes such as organic solvents, polymers, electrolyte solutions, etc. Since the speed of sound is related to binding forces in the medium and the components of the sample, this method allows for a more in-depth understanding of the intermolecular interactions in the sample acquired by N. Chakraborty et al. [4]

Polyethylene glycols in D-mannitol aqueous solutions have been examined for their density and sound speed across a range of temperatures and concentrations. Ultrasonic behavior is one area in which the use of chemicals in medicine is receiving attention. Ultrasonic methods are important to study molecular interactions when paired with other water resources by H. Kaur et al. [5] The various interactions between the molecules in mixes are extensively studied using ultrasonic methods. While analyzing structural properties, volumetric and acoustical properties are crucial. Polyether compounds known as polyethylene glycols have a wide range of uses, from modern manufacturing to medicine. Polyethylene Glycols are a member of the H- (O-CH₂+CH₂)-H-OH polymer family. Due to its remarkable capabilities, the polymer's liquid form has a significant impact on daily living.

Semicarbazide hydrochloride's physicochemical interactions with water and aqueous-carbohydrate (D-xylose/L-arabinose) mixtures were the subject of extensive research by Ankita et al. [6] Using density and ultrasonic velocity data, we determined the apparent molar volume and apparent molar compressibility. These values tell us something about the nature and degree of solute-solvent interactions in the systems under investigation. Recently, these materials have seen a rise in demand in biorefinery, food production, and other biological processes because of their low cost and easy availability. At atmospheric pressure and temperatures, an Anton Paar Lovis 2000 M micro-viscometer was used to gauge the viscosity of semicarbazide hydrochloride in aqueous polysaccharide solutions.

In numerous fields, including electronics, sensors, biomedicine, thermal conductivity, nanofluids, etc., graphene oxide (GO) exhibits extraordinary features examined by A. Jain et al. [7] The original Hummers approach was applied in this study to create GO. The carbon-to-GO transformation was confirmed using a number of different characterization methods, such as FESEM, EDS, FTIR, XRD, and RAMAN. GO suspensions of varying concentrations were made by subjecting the GO to extensive ultrasonication in double-distilled water.

Polyethylene glycol molecular interactions in methanol butylparaben solution were studied by Ashima et al. [8] Understanding thermophysical and thermodynamic properties is crucial for developing models and planning processes in the petrochemical, pharmaceutical, and chemical industries. For the last decade, the acoustic approach has been widely used because of how easily it can determine the thermodynamic parameters of compressed liquids. Studies showing the sensitivity of volumetric parameters to solute-solvent interactions are numerous. Based on the encouraging observations of apparent molar characteristics and partial molar qualities, it was predicted that a significant solute-solvent relationship would manifest.

At a constant temperature of 298 K, the Ostwald's viscometer and the Anton Paar DSA 5000 M density and velocity meter were used to test the density, sound speed, and viscosity of methylparaben samples of varying concentrations. The ultrasonic method is a fantastic instrument for investigating the molecular interactions between polar and non-polar components of a liquid combination. Despite a large body of literature on the molecular interactions in binary liquid mixtures, the features of ternary liquid mixtures have received comparatively little attention. In order to support the examination of the liquid structure by A. Thakur et al. [9] the volumetric and viscometric characteristics of a solution combination were examined.

Using volumetric and acoustic investigations, Ashima et al. [10] are looking into how temperature affects the interaction of sodium ethylparaben with ethylene glycol and propylene glycol. EG is characterized by the presence of two hydroxyl groups (-OH) linked to additional carbon atoms. It contains primary and secondary alcohol functional groups (-OH). The density of the solution mixture grows with increasing ethylene glycol and propylene glycol concentrations while shrinking somewhat with increasing temperature. This article examines the results of volumetric and compressibility experiments conducted on EG and PG at varying concentrations of SEP solution in water. Data analysis shows that important solute-solvent interactions continue to exist. As the SEP concentration in the solution and the glycol molecular weight rise, the interactions between the solute and the solvent become more stable.

The conductance and sound speed of binary aqueous THF solutions containing aluminum sulfate, aluminum nitrate, and aluminum chloride were studied experimentally, and the findings are presented in this article. For a selection of THF compositions and temperatures, we determined the molar conductance, limiting molar conductivity, partial molar isothermal compressibility, and coefficient of adiabatic compressibility. By graphing apparent molar isentropic compressibility data versus molality, we may calculate the slope and partial molar isentropic compressibility. Liquid mixtures, rather than pure liquids, are often employed for purposes in food. Using data analyzed by R.C. Thakur et al. [11]

P. Kaur et al. [12] need knowledge of the mixture's thermodynamic and acoustic properties in order to analyze molecular interactions in liquids. There are many applications for these mixing properties in the chemical and pharmaceutical sectors. "Ultrasonic technology has been shown to effectively expose these characteristics and the nature of molecular interactions in previous studies. The ultrasonic velocity and density of glutaraldehyde solutions of ethylene, diethylene, and triethylene glycol were determined using an Anton Paar DSA 5000 M.

A. Thakur et al. [13] measured the density and sound speed of ethylene, propylene, and Hexylene glycol in methylparaben-methanol solutions at different temperatures and pressures in order to calculate the apparent molar volume and apparent molar isentropic compression of glycols in the binary solvent. Using the complete ternary system, we determined the apparent molar volume and the apparent molar isentropic compressibility at infinite dilution for each of their individual working temperatures. Despite the fact that the effectiveness of parabens as antibacterial agents rises with longer alkyl chains, their lipophilic nature restricts their application. (Methyl-butyl). Because of this, methylparaben and propylparaben are the two parabens most often found in packaged goods and cosmetics.

We perform density and sound velocity measurements of binary mixtures of triethylene glycol across their whole mole fraction range at different temperatures and at a frequency of 2 MHz as a means of reconciling theory and observation, we examine the molecular interactions in the binary mixture. For a complete picture of the physicochemical behavior of liquid mixes. The binding force between the molecules in a mixture affects how quickly ultrasonic waves go through a material. The liquid model postulates that molecules are loosely packed and have space to move in a liquid state. Intermolecular free space and its accompanying properties, which N. Chakraborty et al. were able to identify when liquids are mixed, are used to characterize the interaction that takes place in the mixture in some detail [14]

Utilizing acoustic and volumetric techniques, we analyzed the temperature dependency of interactions between EG, DEG, and TEG and physiologically active D-Panthenol. D-Panthenol aqueous solutions were studied by N. Chakraborty et al. [15] to determine the density of ethylene, diethylene and triethylene glycols (EG, DEG, TEG). Density measurements (both volumetric and acoustic) have been used to analyze EG, DEG, and TEG in D-Panthenol-containing water solutions. Using the data on the speed of sound, we determined the partial molar isentropic compression and the partial molar isentropic compression of transfer. The interaction coefficients between pairs and three groups are also calculated. We may learn more about the molecular interactions between the different components by analyzing the acoustic and thermodynamic characteristics of liquid mixtures. The thermodynamic characteristics and molecular interactions of the liquids are predicted to be strongly correlated. The underlying relationships and structure of the system have a big influence on how fast the sound moves.

Using density and ultrasonic speed measurements recorded at different temperatures and experimental pressure $p = 0.1$ MPa, K. Kaur et al. [16] began to investigate the intermolecular interactions between glycerol and two polyethylene glycols. To detect the interactions between various chemical substances and their liquid mixtures, a solid understanding of thermodynamic properties is required. As liquid mixes are formed, the molecular interaction is altered, and apparent differences in component packaging result. Temperature and glycerol concentration is correlated with increasing levels of ultrasonic speed. The three-dimensional network of hydrogen bonding that makes up the structure of water is connected to the temperature dependence of the ultrasonic speed values, which is a property of water. Any solution that has a faster ultrasonic speed has molecules that are more tightly bound together. The improved correlation is caused by hydrogen bonding within and between the molecules of the solute and the solvent.

Liquid water is the only solvent with the small size and quadrupole moment necessary to allow extensive hydrogen-bonding networks. Multiple studies by K. Kaur et al. [17] have looked at the characteristics of molecular interactions between polar organic liquids and water. Mixed solvents are more useful than pure liquids in a variety of chemistry, pharma, and industrial processes because of the flexibility they provide in terms of combination compositions of two or more components in varying quantities. This permits the estimated properties to be continuously updated.

The density and ultrasonic speed of ethylene glycol, diethylene glycol, and triethylene glycol were measured the apparent, partial, and partial molar volumes of transfer for glycols from water to aqueous glycerol solutions have been computed using the density data. Due to the presence of two hydroxyl groups, all glycols fall under the category of alcohol. Glycols have piqued the interest of scientists because of their common applications in the food, biotechnology, pharmaceutical, and cosmetics industries. Because of their H-bonding, these hygroscopic compounds dissolve entirely in water and other polar solvents. Glycols are added to water-based liquids to lower the freezing point because their hydrogen bonds are disrupted when they dissolve in water investigated by K. Kaur et al. [18]

The apparent molar qualities and limiting apparent molar qualities were determined using experimental data by K. Kaur et al. Since these thermodynamic parameters help anticipate how chemicals will mix and how solutes will dissolve in different solvents, knowing them is important for industry. The variation in component packing becomes visible as a result of a shift in molecular interactions that takes place during the production of liquid mixes have been studied by K. Kaur et al. [19] Liquid mixes can be studied volumetrically and acoustically to help determine thermodynamic parameters that are very sensitive to molecule interactions. The cosmetic, pharmaceutical, biotechnology, and food industries all make substantial use of liquid solutions containing glycols.

Using the ultrasonic velocity and density data, K. Kaur et al. [20] determine the acoustic impedance, adiabatic compressibility, and intermolecular free length for liquid mixtures of glycerol and ethylene glycol maintained at a constant temperature. The linear patterns visible across the board suggest molecular interactions.

II. Conclusions

The binary and ternary mixtures' densities, viscosities, and ultrasonic speeds have all been tested. The ultrasonic velocity's dependency on composition and the resultant acoustical parameters shows that there are molecular interactions present in the mixes. The findings are explained in the context of the hydrogen-bonded complexes present in the mixes. For describing the physical characteristics of solutions and molecule structure in these kinds of systems, hydrogen bonding interaction is crucial. By changing the solvent, temperature, and solute concentration in these systems, subsequent research might learn more about the sorts of interactions that exist between the constituent molecules. Determining the ultrasonic velocity in a given medium is an excellent method for elucidating the medium's physical properties. These chemicals are used in the food preservation process either directly or indirectly. Seeing as that everyone is currently concerned about their health, this issue touches on problems on a global scale. Everyone wants food that is safe, secure, and preserved. These chemicals keep food preserved for a long period. These days, the majority of food is packaged, making it quite safe for everyone to consume top-quality preserved food.

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IV. Conflicts of Interest

“The authors declare no conflict of interest.” The authors clarify that they have no affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with any financial interest or non-financial interest.

REFERENCES:

1. H. Kaur, N. Chakraborty, K. C. Juglan, H. Kumar, “Study of Molecular Interaction of PEG-200 and PEG-600 in Aqueous D-Mannitol Solutions at Different Temperatures,” Letters in Applied Nano bioscience, vol.12, pp. 52, March 2022.
2. P. Patnaik, N. Chakraborty, K.C. Juglan, H. Kumar, “Thermodynamic and Acoustic Studies of Glycols in Aqueous Solutions of Niacin,” Applied NanoBioScience, vol. 12, pp. 171, December 2022.
3. H. Kaur, P. Patnaik, H. Kumar, “Study of Molecular interactions of glycols with D-Mannitol at different temperature,” Journal of Physics: Conference Series, vol. 2267, pp. 012047, June 2021.
4. N. Chakraborty, K.C. Juglan, H. Kumar, “Effect of ethylene glycol/diethylene glycol/triethylene glycol on the thermodynamics of the aqueous biotin solutions at various temperatures,” J. Chem. Thermodynamics, vol. 163, pp. 106584, December 2021.
5. H. Kaur, N. Chakraborty, K.C. Juglan, P. Kaur, H. Kumar, “Study of Molecular Interaction of PEG-200 and PEG-600 in Aqueous D-Mannitol Solutions at Different Temperatures,” Journal of Solution Chemistry, vol. 50, pp. 1079-1102, July 2021.
6. Ankita, D. Chand, A. K. Nain, “Molecular interactions of drug semicarbazide hydrochloride in aqueous-D-xylose/L-arabinose solutions at different temperatures Volumetric, acoustic and viscometric study,” J. Chem. Thermodynamics, vol. 146, pp. 106106, July 2021.
7. A. Jain; K.C. Juglan, “Synthesis and Ultrasonic Investigation of Graphene Oxide Nanosuspension with Water,” Plant Archives, vol. 20, pp. 2586-2593, January 2022.
8. Ashima, K.C. Juglan, H. Kumar, “Intermolecular investigation of polyethylene glycols with butyl paraben in methanol medium attributing volumetric, ultrasonic and thermo- physical properties,” Journal of Molecular Liquids, vol. 298, pp. 112000, January 2020.
9. A. Thakur, H. Kaur, N. Chakraborty, K.C. Juglan, H. Kumar, “Molecular interactions in ternary system of ethane-1, 2-diol with methanol and methyl 4-hydroxybenzoate at 298 K: An acoustic approach,” Journal of Physics: Conference Series, vol. 1531, pp. 012017, 2020.
10. Ashima, K.C. Juglan, H. Kumar, “Ultrasonic and volumetric behavior of glycols with sodium ethylparaben in aqueous medium from T = 293.15 to 308.15 K at atmospheric pressure,” Results in Chemistry, vol. 2, pp. 100049, January 2020.
11. P. Kaur, N. Chakraborty, K.C. Juglan, H. Kumar, “Volumetric and ultrasonic studies of molecular interactions of glycols in aqueous glutaraldehyde solutions at different temperatures,” Journal of Molecular Liquids, vol. 315, pp. 113763, October 2020

12. R. C. Thakur, R. Sharma, A. Sharma, "Molecular interactions analysis of some aluminum salts in binary aqueous solutions of tetrahydrofuran (THF): Acoustic and Conductometric approach," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 1531, pp. 012112, 2020.
13. A. Thakur, K.C. Juglan, H. Kumar, K. Kaur, "Investigation on molecular interaction of glycols in methanol solutions of methylparaben (methyl 4 – hydroxybenzoate) at different temperatures through thermo-acoustical analysis," *Journal of Molecular Liquids*, vol, 288, pp. 111014, August 2019.
14. N. Chakraborty, P. Kaur, K. Kaur, K.C. Juglan, H. Kumar, "Theoretical and experimental ultrasonic velocities Comparison of binary mixtures of triethylene glycols and glycerol at different temperatures," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 1531, pp. 012014, 2020.
15. N. Chakraborty, H. Kumar, K. Kaur, K.C. Juglan, "Acoustic and thermodynamic study of D-Panthenol in aqueous solutions of glycol at different temperatures," *J. Chem. Thermodynamics*, vol. 126, pp. 137-146, November 2018.
16. K. Kaur, K. C. Juglan, H. Kuma, "Acoustical and volumetric investigation of polyethylene glycol 400 and polyethylene glycol 4000 in aqueous solutions of glycerol at different temperatures," *J. Chem. Thermodynamics*, vol. 127, pp. 8-16, December 2018.
17. K. Kaur, K. C. Juglan, H. Kumar, I. Behal, "Thermodynamic Interactions Study of Some Ethylene Glycols in Aqueous Aniline Solutions at Different Temperatures: An Acoustical and Volumetric Approach," *Journal of Chemical & Engineering Data*, vol. 63, pp. 3237–3251, August 2018.
18. K. Kaur, I. Behal, K.C. Juglan, H. Kumar, "Volumetric and ultrasonic studies on interactions of ethylene glycol, diethylene glycol and triethylene glycol in aqueous solutions of glycerol at temperatures $T = (293.15 \text{ K } 308.15) \text{ K}$," *J. Chem. Thermodynamics*, vol. 125, pp. 93-106, October 2018.
19. K. Kaur, K. C. Juglan, H. Kumar, "Investigation on Temperature-Dependent Volumetric and Acoustical Properties of Homologous Series of Glycols in Aqueous Sorbitol Solution," *Journal of Chemical & Engineering*, vol. 62, pp. 3769–3782, October 2017.
20. K. Kaur, K.C. Juglan, H. Kumar, "Thermo-acoustical Molecular Interaction Study in Binary mixtures of glycerol and ethylene glycol" *American Institute of Physics (AIP)*, vol. 1860, pp. 020026, November 2016.

The logo for IJRTI is a large, light blue watermark in the background. It features a stylized lightbulb shape with a circular top and a semi-circular base. Inside the circle, there are three vertical lines of varying heights, resembling a molecular structure or a signal. Below the circle is a grey rectangular box containing the text 'IJRTI' in white, bold, sans-serif capital letters. Below the box is a grey semi-circle.

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